

A Novel Toughening System for Thermoset Resins and its Composites

Louis Boogh, Bo Pettersson†, Sonia Japon and Jan-Anders Månson*
Laboratoire de Technologie des Composites et Polymères
Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, CH-1015 Lausanne, Switzerland
† Perstorp Polyols, Application Technology, S-28480 Perstorp, Sweden

ABSTRACT

Thermoset matrices are widely used in composite applications due to their superior thermomechanical properties and favorable impregnation characteristics. However, the toughness, affecting the impact resistance, fatigue behavior and damage tolerance among other properties, often limits their applicability. A novel toughening system based on a phase separation process is presented in this paper. K_{Ic} toughness values are improved by over 150% for a typical commercial epoxy resin, without other thermomechanical properties and the processability being affected. This toughening system can be applied to a variety of thermosetting materials by adjusting chemical parameters to control phase interactions and reactivity, and thus the final morphology of the modified matrix material.

INTRODUCTION

The objective is to obtain a sustainable toughening effect without affecting the processability of the uncured resins and the thermomechanical properties of the cured material. This is achieved with an initially homogeneous system avoiding the filtration effect during fiber impregnation, followed by a phase separation upon resin curing. Both the curing and the phase separation kinetics influence the processing conditions of the composites, as well as the morphology of the secondary phase in the matrix. The final structure will determine the mechanical performance of the cured resins. Using hyperbranched molecules, the chemical architecture of the shell can be adapted to the various thermosetting resins without affecting the mechanical performances of the bulk. Reactive thermosetting groups are grafted on the shell to ensure a stress transfer between the modifier and the matrix. The toughening mechanisms and properties for thermosetting resins are discussed. Using a model system based on a commercial epoxy resin, the influence of the processing conditions is studied and a processing window is established in the form of a time-temperature-transformation (TTT) diagram. The effect of the bulk structure and chemical architecture of the shell are also discussed.

RESULTS

Toughness of a commercial epoxy resin is increased from a K_{Ic} value of $0.63 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for the neat epoxy resin to $1.54 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for the same resin with only 5% of a hyperbranched molecule modifier. This corresponds to a 2.5 fold increase of the K_{Ic} value, and a 6 fold increase for the G_{Ic} value respectively. The toughening does not affect the Young's modulus or the glass transition temperature of the resin system. The multifunctional hyperbranched polymer used as a modifier phase separates during curing of the thermosetting resin.

(*) to whom correspondence should be addressed

composite plies, or fiber strands, should be avoided during the penetration of the matrix into the fiber bed. This is required in order to obtain toughening properties at all structural levels, even within the fiber bundles. If toughening is induced by particles larger than the average fiber spacing (usually 5-10 μm), these will be filtered out by the proximity of the fiber strands in the reinforcement plies. Thus, within the plies no toughening is effective, and in the interply region, weak zones might appear due to the agglomeration of toughening particles.

The aim is therefore to obtain a sustainable toughening effect without affecting the viscosities of the uncured resins and the thermomechanical properties of the cured material. This should be achieved with an initially homogeneous system avoiding the filtration effect during fiber impregnation, and with a system applicable to the wide variety of thermosetting materials actually used as composite matrices.

APPROACH

A liquid toughening agent, compatible with the uncured thermosetting resin must be used in order to have a homogeneous system during impregnation. Subsequently, the phase separation should only be induced upon curing. A relatively high molecular weight toughening agent will facilitate the control of the phase separation process and increase the effectiveness as a toughener. However, high molecular weights imply a high viscosity which is to be avoided. In order to implement both requirements, low viscosities and a high molecular weight, a spherical molecular structure as opposed to a linear structure would be most suitable. Dendritic polymers possess this spherical structure (see Fig. 1) and have shown a lower viscosity than linear polymers with identical molecular weights [2]. Similar properties are also achieved for some hyperbranched polymers with core/shell structures [3] resembling the architecture of dendrimers. The mechanical properties of these molecules will largely be determined by the bulk properties. On the other hand, the chemical structure of the shell will define the phase separation process. Both the curing and the phase separation kinetics influence the processing conditions of the composites, as well as the structure of the secondary phase in the matrix. Consecutively, the obtained structure will determine the mechanical performance of the cured resins. The chemical architecture of the shell can be adapted to various thermosetting resins without affecting the mechanical performances of the bulk. Reactive groups with the thermosetting matrix should be grafted on the shell to ensure a stress transfer between the modifier and the matrix.

Figure 1. A dendritic molecular structure characterized by the core (I), the bulk (II), and the shell (III).

Hyperbranched molecules consist of a multifunctional core, one or several layers of repeating units building up the bulk structure, and a shell with an adaptable chemical structure. The toughening mechanisms and properties for thermosetting resins are investigated. Using a model system based on a commercial epoxy resin, the influence of the processing conditions is studied and a processing window is established in the form of a time-temperature-transformation (TTT) diagram. The effect of the bulk structure and chemical architecture of the shell are also discussed.

PHASE SEPARATION KINETICS

The phase separation process depends on the chemical nature of the components, and is kinetically controlled by the curing advancement. It determines the resulting structure which consecutively is responsible for the final mechanical properties. Thus, the chemistry-process-structure-properties relations are largely influenced by the phase separation kinetics.

The phase separation will occur through a nucleation and growth phenomena or a spinodal decomposition [4,5,6], depending on the initial composition and the ratio of the phase separation rate, (dps/dt) , over the polymerization rate, (dp/dt) , of the matrix material. If this ratio, $(dps/dt)/(dp/dt)$, is small, spinodal decomposition will occur. This is not desirable since it usually induces a considerable reduction of the thermomechanical properties of the cured modified matrix, due to a higher residual miscibility of the modifier in the main phase. If the $(dps/dt)/(dp/dt)$ ratio is large, the phase separation occurs under equilibrium conditions following the binodal distribution curve and a minimum residual miscibility is obtained. In between these two extreme cases, the nucleation and growth process results in a limited amount of residual miscibility. The desired phase separation process will be controlled by the nucleation and growth of modifier particles. The rate of homogeneous nucleation can be expressed as [7]:

$$dP(r_c) / dt = N_0 D_{AB} \exp(-\Delta G_c / kT) \quad (1)$$

r_c is the critical radius, N_0 is an adjustable pre-exponential factor, D_{AB} is the diffusion coefficient, and ΔG_c is the free energy barrier at r_c . The growth rate can be expressed as [7]:

$$r' dr' / dt = D_{AB} (\varnothing_2 - \varnothing_2^{eq}) \quad (2)$$

r' is the actual radius of the dispersed phase particle, and $(\varnothing_2 - \varnothing_2^{eq})$ is the difference between the actual composition and the equilibrium composition. The latter represents the driving force for the particle growth. In the case of a large $(dps/dt)/(dp/dt)$ ratio, the driving force is small and growth is inhibited. However, nucleation is still active and a bimodal distribution of particle sizes will be obtained. Both the nucleation and growth rates depend strongly on the diffusion constant. The latter may be expressed following the Stokes-Einstein relation [8]:

$$D_{AB} = kT / 6\pi R_2 \eta_1 \quad (3)$$

R_2 is the molecular radius of the dispersed phase, and η_1 is the viscosity of the matrix which is a function of the temperature and the extent of reaction. Thus, the size of the hyperbranched molecule will strongly influence the phase separation process, modifying the nucleation and growth rates due to its influence on the diffusion coefficient. The viscosity at the cloud point at which the phase separation initiates is thus also very important. However, it should be noted that as long as the phase separation process does not become diffusion controlled and no spinodal decomposition is initiated, there is an increase in the concentration of dispersed particles with decreasing cure temperature although the viscosity increases. This is due to the fact that the polymerization rate increases faster with the curing temperature than the nucleation rate [9].

EXPERIMENTAL

Various epoxy functional hyperbranched molecules have been synthesized following a procedure described by Hult et al [10]. The shell chemistry and the bulk structure influences are determined. These materials are described in the following section. A three generation hyperbranched molecule with a tetra-functional core is chosen as the reference modifier. Its shell is functionalised with hydroxyl groups and secondary epoxy groups for which the epoxy ring is shielded. These materials are blended with a DGEBF commercially available epoxy resin (LY5082, Ciba-Geigy). The modified resin is cured isothermally with an isophorondiamine hardener after having been degassed under vacuum for 5 minutes. The hardener is added in stoichiometric proportions. A blend with 5% of the reference modifier is

used for the characterization of the processing window, and to illustrate the influence of the processing conditions on the morphology and mechanical properties.

The phase separation process is characterized by turbidimetry. Rheological data, viscosity evolution, gelation and vitrification times, are obtained using a parallel plate shear rheometer (Rheometrics RDA-II) at 1 Hz under isothermal conditions. The gelation time is determined at a shear storage modulus (G') of 10 Pa. The vitrification time is determined at $\tan\delta=1$. Curing kinetics, i.e. the extent of reaction as a function of time, are analyzed by differential scanning calorimetry (Perkin-Elmer DSC-7) under isothermal conditions. Thermo-mechanical properties, modulus and glass transition temperatures, are determined using a Rheometrics RSA-II equipment in three point bending at 1 Hz and a heating rate of 5 °C/min. Structural analysis of the modified epoxy matrix is performed optically on 5 μm thick microtomed sections, and on fracture surfaces using a scanning electron microscope (Cambridge S100). Tensile and compact tension (CT) specimens are used for mechanical assessment of the modified matrix materials. These samples are tested according to ASTM standards at room temperature on a conventional UTS tensile testing equipment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Polar and reactive hyperbranched molecules with primary epoxy groups grafted on the shell are initially miscible and do not phase separate. The toughening effect in this case remains moderate. With 25% of modifier, the K_{Ic} stress intensity factor increases from 0.63 $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for the neat resin, to 0.83 $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for the modified resin system. However, the toughening effect is accompanied by a decrease in the final glass transition temperature from 104°C to 85°C due to the epoxy network modification by this fully miscible modifier. The initial miscibility can be attributed to the polarity. The absence of phase separation as curing proceeds is due to the network formation, linking the hyperbranched molecules in the initial stages already, due to the high reactivity of the primary epoxy groups.

On the other hand, less polar and less reactive hyperbranched molecules used as reference modifier, and described in the experimental section, will induce a phase separation and a 2.5 fold increase in the K_{Ic} values, from 0.63 $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for the neat resin to 1.54 $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for the modified resin. This represents a 6 fold increase in the energy release rate G_{Ic} from 0.12 kJ/m^2 for the neat resin to 0.72 kJ/m^2 for the modified resin. Using a 10% and 15% volume content of modifier, the K_{Ic} values are further increased to 1.75 and 2.03 $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ respectively. However, at these amounts, the modulus of 2.9 GPa for the neat and the 5% modified resin, is reduced to 2.6 and 2.4 GPa for the 10% and 15% modified resins respectively.

With 5% fully non-polar hyperbranched molecules, no homogeneous mixture can be obtained under 100°C which is the maximum processing temperature for the epoxy resin used. The toughening is still effective, obtaining a K_{Ic} value of 1.34 $\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. However, starting with an emulsion, composite processing may induce an unfavorable filtering effect as discussed earlier.

With 5% of a less reactive hyperbranched molecule, functionalised with only a few secondary epoxy groups, the toughening becomes less effective due to a limited stress transfer capacity between the epoxy matrix and the dispersed modifier phase.

The initial viscosity of the epoxy resin modified with 5% of the reference modifier is very low and remains under 100 mPas at room temperature. The recommended processing temperature range for this resin lies in the range of 20°C to 100°C. Within this range the viscosities are almost not modified by the presence of the modifier and processability is maintained. Fig.2 represents the time-temperature-transformation diagram of this modified epoxy resin. The successive events occurring during isothermal processing are determined following horizontal lines in the TTT diagram. The events represented are the phase separation behavior as measured by turbidimetry, the iso-viscosity curves at 100, 1000 and 10000 mPas, followed by the gelation and vitrification curves. The end of the phase separation curve corresponds to the limit of the turbidimetry measuring technique when the

material becomes fully opaque. In reality, the phase separation will proceed until the complete gelation at which the diffusion of the modifier molecules in the matrix is inhibited. In the initial stages of curing, a homogeneous liquid phase will only be obtained above 50°C. Composite processing should therefore be performed at higher temperatures if the filtration effect is to be avoided. This lower limiting temperature can be reduced to temperatures below 20°C by using a more polar modifier. The phase separation onset times between 50 and 60°C are longer than 10 minutes allowing most conventional composite processing techniques to be used. From the phase separation onset until the gelation, the structure is evolving, particle dimensions and interparticle distances are fixed. At the different processing temperatures, the times available for particle nucleation and growth become considerably shorter as the temperature is increased. Furthermore, due to the higher temperature the compatibility is increased. At 80°C the phase separation is initiated at a conversion of 37%, as opposed to a conversion of 19% at 60°C. Thus, the secondary epoxy groups on the modifier molecules will have reacted to a larger extent and their diffusion is hampered. However, the viscosity at which the phase separation will take place will be reduced, increasing the diffusion coefficient of the modifier in the resin. These opposite trends will attenuate the influence of the processing temperature on the obtained structures.

Figure 2. Time-Temperature-Transformation (TTT) diagram of the epoxy resin with 5% of the reference modifier. Phase separation, iso-viscosity, gelation and vitrification curves are defined under isothermal curing conditions.

The structures resulting from isothermal curing at different temperatures are shown in Fig.3. It can be seen that for processing under the dissolution temperature of 50°C induces a bimodal particle size distribution. This is due to a large $(dps/dt)/(dp/dt)$ ratio as discussed earlier. The largest particles observed have a diameter of approximately 4.5 μm . This remains small compared to other phase separating systems, due to the large molecular weight of the modifier limiting the diffusion rate. The smaller particles of the 20°C and 40°C cured materials showing a bimodal distribution, and the largest particles obtained with processing at higher temperatures, have diameters less than 1.3 μm . This smaller particle size is independent of the processing temperature. Processing at higher temperatures does however increase the interparticle distances. This may be explained by the increased nucleation rate as described by Eqn(1). The residual miscibility after curing is small for all processing temperatures. This is shown by the fact that the glass transition temperatures and modulus of the cured materials are not influenced by the blending [11]. As a reference, the T_g and modulus of the unmodified epoxy resin are 104°C and 2.9 GPa respectively. Upon curing at

temperatures below 80°C, the resin does not reach the infinite T_g of 104°C. However, this value is approached by postcuring the material at 80°C, without affecting the structure obtained at the curing temperature.

Figure 3. SEM pictures of CT specimens fracture surfaces, illustrating the structure obtained for the epoxy resin with 5% of the reference modifier cured at different temperatures.

Figure 4. Glass transition, T_g (○), and modulus, E (Δ), as a function of the isothermal cure temperature of the epoxy resin with 5% of the reference modifier.

Fig.5 shows a 2.5 fold increase of the K_{Ic} toughness values obtained for the epoxy resin with 5% of the reference modifier compared to the unmodified epoxy resin. However, at 60°C, a minimum K_{Ic} value for the modified resin of 1.27 $MPa\sqrt{m}$ is obtained. This is due to smaller particle sizes compared to the materials cured at lower temperatures, and to a larger interparticle distance compared to the materials cured at higher temperatures. The dependence of the toughness on the respective ratio of the particle size over the interparticle distance has been reported earlier [12]. This relation is verified and depicted in Fig.6 .

The results presented illustrate the effect of toughening a DGEBA epoxy resin with hyperbranched molecules. It should be stressed that the toughening system can be applied to most other thermosetting resins, by adapting the shell chemistry to optimize the phase separation kinetics. Thus, it is possible to obtain the appropriate structure for a maximized toughening effect and to maintain the material's processability. If required, the hyperbranched bulk structure can also be adapted. Its size can be changed to adapt the phase separation rate by modifying the diffusion rate. The processing window of the material studied is suitable for most conventional fiber reinforced composite materials. Furthermore, the modification of the resin does not change the wetting properties of the reinforcing fibers and no phase separation is induced at their surface which could influence the interfacial properties.

Figure 5. The toughness expressed by the stress intensity factor K_{Ic} as a function of the isothermal cure temperatures of the epoxy resin with 5% of the reference modifier (o) and of the unmodified epoxy resin (Δ).

Figure 6. The normalized toughness as a function of the normalized particle reinforcement structure. Normalization is done using the epoxy resin with 5% of the reference modifier cured at 80°C .

CONCLUSION

Toughness of a commercial epoxy resin is increased from a K_{Ic} value of $0.63 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for the neat epoxy resin to $1.54 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for the same resin with only 5% of a hyperbranched molecule modifier. This corresponds to a 2.5 fold increase of the K_{Ic} value, and a 6 fold increase for the G_{Ic} value respectively. The toughening does not affect the Young's modulus or the glass transition temperature of the resin system. The multifunctional hyperbranched polymer used as a modifier phase separates during curing of the thermosetting resin. Hyperbranched molecules have shown to possess a lower viscosity than linear polymers with identical molecular weights and thus larger molecular structures can be used without affecting the viscosity of the uncured resin. This effect can be attributed to the spherical structure of the hyperbranched molecules. The chemical architecture of the shell, i.e. its polarity and reactivity, controls the kinetics of the phase separation process, and can be tailored in order to maintain a wide processing window and to obtain the desired structure for optimum toughness properties. The curing and phase separation kinetics both influence the processability of the toughened epoxy, and the secondary phase structure. The obtained structure will in turn determine the mechanical performance of the cured resins. The processing window of the material studied makes it suitable for most conventional processing techniques used for fiber reinforced composite. By adapting the shell chemistry, this modifier system may also be used for other thermosetting resins.

REFERENCES

1. R. A. Pearson, Sources of toughness in modified epoxies, *Ph.D. thesis, Univ. of Michigan* (1990)
2. B. Pettersson and K. Sörensen, High-solid alkyds based on hyperbranched polymers, *21st Waterborne, higher-solids and powder coatings symp. proc.* **2**, 753-764 (1994)
3. D. A. Tomalia, A. M. Naylor and W. A. Goddard III, Starburst dendrimers, *Angew. Chem. Ed. Eng.* **29**, 138-175 (1990)
4. L. A. Utracki, Polymer alloys and blends, *Ed.: L. A. Utracki, publ.: Hanser* (1989)
5. J.-F. Hwang, J. A. Manson, R. W. Hertzberg, G. A. Miller and L. H. Sperling, Structure-property relationships in rubber-toughened epoxies, *Pol. Eng. and Sci.* **29**, 1466-1476 (1989)
6. C. B. Bucknall and I. K. Partridge, Phase separation in crosslinked resins containing polymeric modifiers, *Pol. Eng. and Sci.* **26**, 54-62 (1986)
7. S. M. Moschiar, C. C. Riccardi, R. J. J. Williams, D. Verchere, H. Sautereau and J. P. Pascault, Rubber-modified epoxies. III., *J. of Appl. Pol. Sci.* **42**, 717-735 (1991)
8. L. T. Manzione, J. K. Gillham and C. A. McPherson, Rubber-modified epoxies. I., *J. of Appl. Pol. Sci.* **26**, 889-905 (1981)
9. A. Vazquez, A. J. Rojas, H. E. Adabbo, J. Borrajo and R. J. J. Williams, Rubber-modified thermosets: prediction of the particle size distribution of dispersed domains, *Polymer* **28**, 1156-1164 (1987)
10. A. Hult, M. Johansson, E. Malmström, K. Sörensen, PCT/SE93/00148
11. L. T. Manzione, J. K. Gillham and C. A. McPherson, Rubber-modified epoxies. II., *J. of Appl. Pol. Sci.* **26**, 907-919 (1981)
12. D. Verchere, J. P. Pascault, H. Sautereau, S. M. Moschiar, C. C. Riccardi and R. J. J. Williams, Rubber-modified epoxies. II., *J. of Appl. Pol. Sci.* **42**, 701-716 (1991)

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Perstorp Polyols is acknowledged for the financial support and the permission to publish this work. Prof. A. Hult of the Royal Institute of Technology of Stockholm is also acknowledged for the fruitful and inspiring discussions.